

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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Abstract:

In this article, there is an opinion about the methods of teaching grammar in teaching English to students and comments are made. Grammar is the foundation of any language and is crucial to effective communication plays a role. English grammar to students in teaching English as a second language it is necessary to use effective methods that help to understand its subtleties. To the students to make the learning process interesting and effective by exploring different ways of teaching grammar are important factors.

Key words: traditional grammar, systematic approach, grammar rules, grammar concepts, writing, speaking, communicative language, modern technology.

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Traditional grammar teaching involves direct teaching of grammar rules and concepts includes. It focuses on memorization, exercises and exercises. This method is often although criticized for being boring and harsh, it can be effective when used in moderation. The key is to balance it with more interactive and interesting techniques:

- Provides a systematic approach to learning grammar.
- Helps students understand grammar rules and regulations.
- Facilitates grammatical accuracy in writing and speaking.

Communicative language teaching emphasizes real-life communication rather than memorizing grammar will give. Grammar focuses on the use of language to achieve practical communication goals taught in context. Encourage students to speak, listen, read and write in meaningful contexts will be done.

- Encourages active use of language.
- Develops practical communication skills.
- It provides a more engaging and interactive learning experience.

May not cover all grammar rules comprehensively. Some students may struggle with fluency if they do not have a solid grammatical foundation.

Schechter's method. This is a modern method, very different from the classical methods of learning English is different. Individual and motivated research is required from each student. Class discussion, current events, hobbies, lifestyle, future goals of students passes in the form of doing.

Lex program. This technique is for those who already know English, how to make sentences correctly useful for those who know how to compose and understand grammar. You program the computer or you install it on your laptop and start reading. It is necessary to remember to repeat on the monitor you will see words, sentences, phrases (written and spoken). Together with the study material. There are tests to determine your level in Lex. In

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addition to learning English, this the technique sharpens the memory, which is useful for students of different ages.

Muller's method. This innovative technique explores the conscious and unconscious aspects of our thinking covers Stanislav Müller activates previously hidden possibilities through this method turned to neuropsychological methods to help. It is based on two methods - the holographic memory method and the learning system: Holographic memory by separating the main thing from the student helps to show, develop the ability to intensively learn new material. The student begins to logically build the flow of knowledge, systematizing its every detail is convenient for him. The Muller system allows you to speed up the learning process. material it is easier, faster to digest and thereby saves energy. The technique is for students aged 16-18 is ideal. Task-based language teaching is a learner-centered approach that integrates grammar naturally into tasks and activities. Students are given tasks such as solving problems, creating projects, or completing role-play scenarios. This is the grammar is learned in the process of completing assignments. Real-life problem solving and critical thinking develops thinking. Grammar is taken in context, making it more relevant. Encourages collaboration and creativity. Grammar instruction may not be as clear as in traditional methods. Some students may need extra help to understand complex grammatical concepts. Grammar in context is a method in which students use grammar naturally involves introducing authentic texts such as articles, stories or dialogues. Students learn to identify and analyze grammatical structures in the context of a text. This text-based discussions and activities help reinforce their understanding.

- Encourages reading and comprehension skills.
- Shows how grammar is used in real life situations.
- Helps students to understand grammar rules intuitively.

Using technology and games makes learning grammar more fun. Learning apps, online quizzes and interactive games can be used to reinforce grammar concepts in a fun and interactive way. This method is especially young interests students.

- Increases motivation and activity.
- Enables self-directed learning.
- Provides immediate feedback.

It should be used as a supplement to other methods, not a replacement. Excessive use of technology can lead to passive learning.

Conclusion: Teaching English language learners grammar requires a balanced approach that takes into account their needs, preferences and learning styles. Although traditional methods still have their place, communicative language teaching, task Modern approaches such as language teaching and incorporating technology into lessons are based on grammar makes learning more interesting and relevant. Ultimately, it's up to the specific needs of the students A combination of these adapted methods is often used in the context of English language teaching is the most effective way to teach grammar.

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